

**A Mechanistic Road Map for the *in situ* Metamorphic Anti-coronaviral Quinine Based
Drugs and New Generation Drug Hypothesis**

Rıdvan SAY, Ph. D.

Honorary Scientist and Consultant / Bionkit Co. Ltd. Eskişehir, Turkey

“Manuscript contains 3664 words without References”

Rıdvan SAY, Ph. D.

Honorary Scientist and Consultant / Bionkit Co. Ltd.

Anadolu University Anadolu Technopark No: 212

Eskişehir, Turkey

e-mail: ridvansayy@gmail.com

A Mechanistic Road Map for the in situ Metamorphic Anti-coronaviral Quinine Based Drugs and New Generation Drug Hypothesis

ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 outbreak, which has occurred all over the world for the last 5-6 months, the painful events of this epidemic to the public, and the difficult situations that scientists have experienced in terms of solutions in this context have made it necessary for me to share this. With this study, an approach was introduced to the availability of quinine-based derivatives within the framework of this disease by explaining the COVID-19 hypothesis.

In this hypothesis, it has been strongly recommend that quinine-based herbal remedies are an inexpensive and accessible anti-coronal medicine for the treatment of COVID-19. COVID-19 can be inhibited via many different target areas, nsps, and enzymes by using mechanism-based hypotheses. And with this hypothesis, scientists and drug developers are urged to take new steps, considering these hypotheses in order to develop new drug types. It should be known that the quinine derivatives-based approach will be useful with different mechanisms than hydroxychloroquine treatment and anti-malarial treatment.

Here, it has been described as a novel in situ approach (isTE) for chemical blocking of thiols of viruses' enzymes through ROS radicals and enzymes mediated thio-ene in situ reaction in virus-cell biomicro-environment. And here, it has been suggested, an enzyme-mediated and/or zinc ionophore mediated multi-targeted enzymes inhibiting process using quinine based old drugs at biomicro-environmental conditions. And the new mode "*in situ* metamorphic drugs" can be utilized as a new COVID-19 treatment model for the selective blocking of proteolytic processing of the nonstructural (ns) polyprotein.

Also, as a highly accurate prediction, the quinine based approach can prevent coronavirus entry and some hemolytic damages caused by heme-mediated oxidative stress, vascular inflammation, heme- induced coagulation activation.

Keywords: COVID-19, quinine-based derivatives, nsps, "*in situ* metamorphic drug" hypothesis, in situ thiol-ene (isTE).

Introduction

The rapid spread of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19), caused by the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) first seen in China in December 2019, has become a pandemic. Under these circumstances, awareness 2019-nCoV's scientific features and anecdotally represented findings regarding therapy should be updated continuously and needs to be summarized. Perspectives should be explained to help designing therapeutics, to take public actions and discover new scientific routes-against incoming epidemics.

Recently, Chloroquine and similar components are attracting enormous attention from the scientific community. Chloroquine has been found to be efficient on SARS-CoV-2 in cultured cells and reported to be efficient in about 100 Chinese COV-19 patients [1, 2]. Gautret et al. [3] in France reported that the antimalaria drug hydroxychloroquine alone and in combination with azithromycin could prove to be an effective treatment for the coronavirus (CoV) infections that are the cause of COVID-19, for the case of the 20 patients. And then, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) declared an Emergency Use Authorization (EUA) for use of oral formulations of chloroquine phosphate and hydroxychloroquine sulfate for the possible treatment of 2019 coronavirus (COVID-19).

Chloroquine is metabolized by a lysosome-dependent mechanism of intracellular degradation and known to accumulate in the acidic food vacuoles of *Plasmodium* parasites which are caused by Malaria, which feeds on the hemoglobin and forms a granular pigment called hemozoin. When chloroquine binds to heme, hemozoin cannot be formed, forcing the parasite to die in its own waste. On the other hand, since the accumulated ferriprotoporphyrin IX (FP) from hemoglobin is available to bind chloroquine, Chou and Fitch have suggested that it is the mediator of the antimalarial activity of chloroquine [4,5]. Also, it has been suggested that the use of chloroquine will increase vesicular pH, thereby eliminating SARS CoV infection by possible prevention of virus-receptor binding-interaction [6]. Similar to its potential role in malaria treatment, chloroquine causes increment in endosomal pH and interferes between angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE 2), and cell surface binding sites for Spike (S) protein of SARS-CoV. In addition, chloroquine has also been reported to act as a zinc ionophore and inhibit viral RNA dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) which has been suggested as a potential mechanism of action on COVID-19 [7,8].

Similar to chloroquine, another anti-malarial drug, hydroxychloroquine (HCQ) is known to increase lysosomal pH and HCQ is a weak base that is known to elevate the pH of acidic intracellular organelles [9]. HCQ is also known to inhibit cytokine production through the toll-like receptor (TLR) family receptors and cytokine storm have been reported in SARS-CoV-2

infection [10, 11]. In addition, supplementation of zinc has been demonstrated to decrease reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the generation of inflammatory cytokines by upregulating A20, a zinc transcription factor, which inhibits the activation of NF- κ B [12]. Furthermore, pyrithione based zinc ionophores have been reported at low concentrations inhibits the replication of RNA viruses, especially SARS coronavirus (SARS-CoV) [13-15].

The discovery of quinine and its derivatives is considered a miraculous finding from as early as the 1600s and malaria treatment with quinine, as a component of the bark of the cinchona (quina-quina) tree. Cinchona alkaloids in the bark of cinchona including quinine, quinidine, cinchonine, and cinchonidine are all effective against malaria (Fig 1). In 1820, quinine was extracted from the bark and purified quinine then replaced the bark as the standard treatment for malaria [16].

Quinine can be absorbed rapidly both orally and parenterally, reaching peak concentrations within 1-3 hours and its half-life is between 11-18 hours. The use of overdose of quinine derivatives leads to the pathological condition of cinchonism. Tinnitus, slight impairment of hearing, headache, and nausea have also been observed. Hypotension and hypoglycemia can be seen as other side effects [16-21].

In December 2019, several pneumonia cases arose in Wuhan, with an infectious acute respiratory infection. Later the reason behind this pneumonia disguise discovered as a new member of the coronavirus family. Since then, the COVID-19 has no known effective treatment. Therefore, the need of cure has raised the urgency for novel drug discovery approaches [22]. With these possible cases and scientific motivations, quinine derivatives need to be considered to cope with COVID-19 treatments.

The purpose of this article is to discuss and question the usability of quinine-based herbal derivatives which are cheap, easily accessible for emergency solutions. The aim is to provide a synergistic approach to scientists, field workers, and people by explaining the hypothesis for COVID-19.

Hypothesis - Possible Mechanisms of the Availability of Quinine and Its Derivatives to Fight against Covid-19

A CoV is nothing like *Plasmodium* related to malaria. And a CoV is not even a cell. Rather, it is a positive strand of RNA virus and its RNA encapsulated in a bubble-like membrane of lipid and protein. To reproduce themselves, a CoV must enter the host cell and use the host's infrastructure. The coronavirus RNA has the largest genome among all RNA viruses (125 nm

in diameter) and its host interactions include CoV replication and inhibiting of the host's defenses which are key to viral pathogenesis [23, 24]. While the genes for non-structural proteins (nsps) constitute two-thirds of the CoV genome, the other third of the viral genome encodes four "structural" proteins which are spike (S), envelope (E), membrane (M), and nucleocapsid (N). The M and E proteins are involved in viral assembly, while the N protein is incorporated for RNA genome assembly. The S protein is a surface located trimeric glycoprotein of CoV, which plays a functional role in viral entry into host cells, eventually causes viral infection. Like other coronaviruses, the 2019-nCoV uses the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of the S protein to engage Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) which is an enzyme that influences blood pressure. Peptides used as therapeutics are essential tools to block RBD–ACE2 binding and inhibit the production of S protein and functional S1 and S2 subunits [22, 25-27]

By analyzing this RBD–ACE2 and other interactions and since we know the enemy, its biomicro-environment between the virus and our cells, how and which mechanisms of quinine and its derivatives (available drug but refreshed effective mechanisms and suggestions) can be useful in fighting against COVID-19 and its incoming mutations?

pH Effect of Quinine

Chemically, quinine is a weak base [28] and accumulates extensively in cell membranes [29]. CoV enters a host cell through an endosome vesicle formed from the membrane. As endosomes become less acidic, the proteins of CoV inside can be inactivated or partially denatured, because of quinine and its derivatives changed the pH of the endosomes carrying viruses.

Biomicro-environment between the virus and our cells

Nod-like receptor family, pyrin domain-containing 3 (NLRP3) plays an important role in the recognition of virus infection. To describe the activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome, four models have been proposed thus far: K^+ efflux and Ca^{2+} influx based on viroporins that allow proton flux from the endosome into the viral interior after the virus is taken up into the host cell; cathepsin B and L, which are specific lysosomal cysteine proteases; the release of reactive oxygen species (ROS); activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome by viral RNA and its cleavage products generated by RNase [30-32].

These findings highlight the importance of the release of ROS and cations release from virions, in COVID-19 induced inflammasome activation and in biomicro-environment change after interaction with the virus.

ROS are highly reactive oxygen species e.g, superoxide, singlet oxygen, H₂O₂. Most of the ROS released from neutrophils and macrophages to the plasma are neutralized. However, the un-neutralized ROS in the red blood cells (RBC) has been shown to cause damage in the RBC membrane and also cause inflammation in other cells [33]. By rupturing of RBCs releases high concentrations of heme, which promotes ROS production causing tissue damage and at further cases to death. Also, *in vitro* studies have shown that H₂O₂ has a long half-life in bio-interfaces and can diffuse out of cells, where it can react with free heme with subsequent heme degradation and iron release [34,35].

On the other hand, enzymes, such as peroxidase, glucose oxidase, and hematin, can initiate radical-mediated polymerization reactions, including vinyl chain-growth polymerization and thiol-ene polymerization. Also, enzyme-mediated polymerization is important especially well-suited for *in situ* polymerizations, where the polymer is processed in the medium, where it will be utilized [36,37]. These polymerizations may bring new approaches especially useful for old-novel drugs and drug delivery applications where the drug or inhibitor as “*in situ* metamorphic drug” is formed in the biomicro-environment of cells and viruses and active sites of coronaviruses.

In this article, I report a new generation “*in situ* thiol-ene (isTE)” strategy and design new antivirals based on quinine derivatives and herbal medicines to fight with COVID-19 as “*in situ* metamorphic anticoronavirals” which activate in biomicro-environment of virus-cell.

Our standing point will support my hypothesis is that heme c has covalent thioether bonds formed between cysteine (Cys) side chains and the heme vinyl groups. A nucleophilic mechanism like heme c is possible in between the thiol group of Cys at the active sites of CoV enzymes and a vinyl group of quinine derivatives through thio-ene mechanism [38,39].

Complementary Designs to the Hypothesis

Possible *in situ* Thiol-ene (isTE) Mechanisms at the active sites of the enzymes of quinine derivatives as *in situ* metamorphic drugs

The thiol-ene reaction produces the thioether following the free-radical as well as the ionic mechanism through Markovnikov and anti-Markovnikov additions. The thiol-ene reaction has been utilized for the generation of biomaterials and bioconjugate synthesis and site-specific protein modification [40-44].

Here, it has been described as an in-situ approach for chemical blocking of thiols of viruses' enzymes through ROS radicals and hydronium ions from virion in virus-cell biomicro-environment. Unlike most thiol-ene strategies, the "in situ thiol-ene- isTE" strategy does not utilize the classical "reactant – product" approach to enable drug delivery and *in situ* modification and inhibition of CoV enzymes. It is the first time suggested in this article that a synergistic and multi-targeted inhibition can be used for novel antivirals and in particular, COVID-19. Such an "*in situ* thiol-ene" reaction between a vinyl group bearing quinidine-cinchonidine and quinine-cinchonine alkaloid monomers and in their active sites cysteine having enzymes of viruses (e.g, cysteine proteases) can be organized in conjunction with mediated enzymes, ROS species and/or weak hydronium ions (Fig. 1).

And also, acting as a cofactor, glutathione (GSH) works with enzymes to convert reactive oxygen species (ROS) into a benign species and can be quenched oxidative stress and inflammations through interactions between quinine-based monomers and thiols of GSH's.

Figure 1. The possible in situ thio-ene (isTE) reaction of cysteine with quinine and its derivatives in biomicro-environment.

Active sites blocking of coronaviruses enzymes by using the “in situ thiol-ene -isTE” strategy and in situ metamorphic anticoronals

Upon entry into host cells, the incoming CoV genome is processed by two specific open reading frames (ORFs), ORF1a, and ORF1b, papain-like proteinase (PL^{pro}) and 3C-like proteinase (3CL^{pro}), into 16 mature nonstructural proteins (nsp1–nsp16). Most of the nsps, such as RNA-dependent RNA polymerase, helicase, and proteases, perform necessary functions in the process of viral RNA replication and transcription. The processing of three sites in the nsp1–nsp4 region is maintained by one or two papain-like proteases (PL^{pro}) residing in the very large nsp3 subunit and the SARS-CoV main protease process the replication through three conserved cleavage sites that identified a catalytic triad (Cys-His-Asp) and zinc-binding site [45-49]. The SARS-CoV protease has a high similarity with the 2019-nCoV protease. Also, 3CLP is a cysteine protease found in the CoV polyprotein and cleaves the polyproteins into individual polypeptides [22, 50-52].

On the other hand, Coronaviruses encode multiple interferon antagonists that modulate the host response to virus replication using the deubiquitinase (DUB) within nsp3 and also these papain-like proteases had deubiquitinating and deISGynating activity. Hu et al., showed that the coronavirus N protein is a function of modulating the host's innate immune response. DUBs catalyze the cleavage of ubiquitin from substrate host's proteins and disrupt the immunity of the host through thiol proteases, which rely on a nucleophilic cysteine in the active site for catalysis [53-59]. Besides, it has been observed that SARS-CoV 3CL^{pro} caused a significant increase in ROS production [60].

The coronavirus proteases (papain-like protease (PL^{pro}) and 3C-like protease (3CL^{pro}) and DUBs) can be used as a target for ROS and enzyme-mediated isTE based quinone derivatives as in situ metamorphic antivirals that inhibit the replication and proliferation of 2019- nCoV. I hypothesize that after blocking the cleavage site motif of the coronavirus's cysteine protease, by using ROS and enzyme-mediated isTE reaction, PL^{pro} enzyme may be inhibited, and also the virus can't use a deubiquiting mechanism of IFN-antagonism.

The “in situ thiol-ene” strategy can provide simultaneously radical oxygen mediated thiol quinone and/or quinidine based active site inhibiting of nsPs enzymes such as papain-like protease (PL^{pro}), 3C-like protease (3CL^{pro}) and papain-like protease/deubiquitinase that have cysteine thiol group as the key nucleophile in which the initial steps of the catalytic cleavage of the target peptide bond of the our “host” cells (Fig 2). The vinyl linked quinone based metamorphic inhibitors of the proteases that utilize the isTE mechanism may both inhibit viral replication and suppression of IFN as a synergistic effect.

Fig 2. Possible "isTE" mechanism between quinine derivatives and active sites of PLpro, 3CLpro and PPpro/deubiquitinase

Multipoint Inhibition of Serine Protease, RdRp and Serine rich CoV N based on Zinc mediated Targeting Mechanisms using Zinc-quinine derivatives

The ability of the coronavirus to enter the cells depends on the activation of their envelope glycoproteins by cell proteases. The respective enzymes become excellent targets for antiviral intervention. Coronaviruses can use serine proteases, especially Transmembrane protease serine-type 2 (TMPRSS2), localized at the cell surface and cleaves its S protein and activate binding between virus S protein and host cell receptor, ACE-2. The enzymatic domain of the enzyme contains a catalytic triad of three amino acids (serine, aspartate, and histidine) present in a highly conserved sequence motif [61-63].

The rapid increasing of infected cases suggests that its effective transmission among humans, which largely depends on virus-binding host cell receptors and host cell proteases-cleaving virus spike protein. Due to the important roles of TMPRSSs in 2019-nCoV infection, transmembrane serine protease inhibitors may be the potential antiviral treatment option for 2019-nCoV infection [64,65].

Since several inhibitor molecules show a high affinity for proteases, they can also be a precursor for an inhibitor structure model of serine protease targets. Matriptase as one of them was strongly inhibited by bis(5-amidino-2-benzimidazolyl)methane (BABIM) [66]. Katz et al. [67] proposed a new approach as zinc mediated serine protease inhibitor, in which a Zn^{2+} ion is demonstrated as in between two chelating nitrogens of BABIM and two active site residues His57 and Ser 195. They have revealed that the coordination inhibitor enhances inhibition by over 10^3 fold. Verner et al. [68] illuminated the novel serine protease inhibitors with high-resolution crystal structures, which bind to the catalytic Ser195 through a unique network of short hydrogen bonds among the inhibitor hydroxyl oxygen, Ser195, and a water molecule

trapped in the oxyanion hole. Also, Lee et al. analyzed five active metal-conjugated inhibitors bound with the 3C-like protease of SARS-associated coronavirus through crystallographically. They showed that the complex structures of each Zn^{2+} of the zinc-inhibitors are tetrahedrally coordinated to the histidine and cysteine catalytic dyad [69].

On the other hand, positive-stranded RNA viruses including CoV have developed various replication strategies through RNA-dependent RNA polymerases (RdRp) that are key targets for antiviral research. Zn^{2+} is vitally an important cofactor for numerable viral proteins as well and in cell culture studies, Zn^{2+} concentrations in high amount and the addition of many ligands were observed to inhibit the replication of various RNA viruses. More specifically, Zn^{2+} was found to block the initiation step of RNA synthesis of the SARS-CoV RdRp and the inhibitory effect of the divalent cation could be reversed by chelating Zn^{2+} with MgEDTA. RdRp, also named nsp12 from COVID-19 contains a divalent cation binding residue as aspartate and serine having residues at catalytic site [70-73].

CoV N, another remarkable protein that plays a regulatory role in viral replication, has RNA-binding and chaperone activities, and a serine-rich region that is mostly modified by phosphorylation. In addition, Cong and coworkers identified and created specific N protein point mutants that block its binding to nsp3 in vitro, and they explained that the inhibition of N protein-nsp3 interaction seriously damages viral replication and egression [74-76].

For these reasons, CoV N protein, RdRp (nsp12) and TMPRSS could be synergistic targets for anti-coronaviral therapy using zinc mediated quinine derivatives. Although there are few coordination structure studies on Zn – quinine in the literature, it can be predicted that 1:1 complex is possible [77, 78]. And, for anti-COVID-19 drug design, this Zn^{2+} centered quinine coordination pattern may serve as a starting platform for inhibitor optimization at subphysiological levels (Fig 3.).

Fig 3. Tetrahedrally coordinated 1:1 Zn- quinine complex

The Zn-quinine complex in which Zn^{2+} ion is tetrahedrally coordinated between nitrogens of quinine and two active site residues, histidine and serine residues of a serine protease and/or one active site serine residue of serine protease and CoV N protein and RdRp (=nsp12), could be enhanced and multipoint synergistic inhibition of serine protease and N and nsp12 (Fig 4). Also, quinine and quinidine have a similar structure between indole and benzimidazole, which were also essential components for synergic potency as serine protease inhibitors. The Zn-quinine coordination geometry can provide physiologically Zn^{2+} mediated inhibitors of therapeutically important serine-rich proteins.

Fig. 4. Possible interaction between Zn-quinine and serine (a) and serine-histidine (b) of enzymes

As a result, the serine protease, zinc ionophore, and serine-rich CoV N protein and RNA polymerase-based findings can allow us to study quinine derivatives-based approaches of COVID-19 inactivation in more detail. Additionally, the subphysiological zinc-mediated inhibition of RNA synthesis of COVID-19 described here may provide an alternative approach to highlight the use of quinine-based zinc-ionophores in antiviral therapy. In addition, the zinc-mediated inhibition of RNA synthesis of COVID-19 shown here may achieve an alternative approach to highlight the use of quinine-based zinc-ionophores in antiviral therapy.

The Ability of Quinolines to Prevent Damage Caused By Heme

Based on domain analysis and molecular docking modeling studies of Wenzhong and Hualan, the ORF8 and surface glycoprotein could bind to the iron porphyrin that is, heme. At the same time, orf1ab, ORF10, and ORF3a proteins could coordinate attack the heme that will cause less oxygen and carbon dioxide. And the lung cells have extremely inflammatory which eventually results in ground-glass-like lung images. According to the findings, quinine could prevent the coronavirus from infecting human cells through vinylic interaction to the porphyrin and heme and catching free porphyrins because the COVID's envelope proteins to help the virus enter host cell are dependent on porphyrins (79). On the other hand, heme is cytotoxic and pro-inflammatory and can contribute to organ damage and thrombin generation (80, 81).

Quinolines can also form covalent bonds with heme to incorporate, but the proportion of covalent-bound quinoline–heme versus noncovalent-bound complexes has not been determined (82-84). On the other hand, de Villiers et al. have determined by single-crystal X-ray diffraction the structures of the complexes formed between quinine and quinidine and iron(III) protoporphyrin IX (Fe(III)PPIX). And, they have demonstrated that a three-point interaction exists between Fe(III)PPIX and the quinolines that involve coordination, π -stacking, and intramolecular hydrogen bond formation (85).

As a highly accurate prediction, the quinine based approach can prevent coronavirus entry and some hemolytic damages caused by heme-mediated oxidative stress, vascular inflammation, heme- induced coagulation activation.

Conclusion

At the point we have reached; the outbreak that started in Wuhan in December 2019 spreads rapidly and causes thousands of deaths and also neither a vaccine nor an antiviral drug is close to a pinpoint treatment. In this emergency, as a scientist, I am writing this article without any financial expectation and I believe it is important to share the views and perspectives from an open source. I strongly recommend that quinine-based herbal remedies are an inexpensive and accessible anti-coronal medicine for the treatment of COVID-19 and that COVID-19 can be inhibited via many different target areas, nsps, and enzymes by using mechanism-based hypotheses. And I urge scientists and drug developers to take new steps, considering these hypotheses in order to develop new drug types.

In summary, it should be known that the quinine derivatives-based approach will be useful with different mechanisms than hydroxychloroquine treatment and anti-malarial treatment. Here, it has been described as a novel *in situ* approach (isTE) for chemical blocking of thiols of viruses' enzymes through ROS radicals and enzymes mediated thio-ene *in situ* reaction in virus-cell biomicro-environment. And, I suggest that an enzyme-mediated and/or zinc ionophore mediated multi-targeted enzymes inhibiting process using quinine based old drugs at physiological conditions and biomicro-environmental conditions. And the new mode "*in situ* metamorphic drugs" can be utilized as a new COVID-19 treatment model for the selective blocking of proteolytic processing of the nonstructural (ns) polyprotein.

This strategy can be readily modified the protein systems in a virus where *in situ* inhibition, detection by using the fluorescence, and radio-activated species was accomplished with drug and drug delivery mechanisms based on capping and labeling. This method will find widespread use as it takes advantage of a mechanism accepted by a virus enzyme. Future studies will aim to use alternative labeling reagents (new vinylized drugs, theranostics, new opsonization agent, adjuvant) to enable the use of fluorescent or radioactive assay systems to increase the scope and sensitivity of the described approach.

References

1. Wang, M., Cao, R., Zhang, L., et al. Remdesivir and chloroquine effectively inhibit the recently emerged novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) in vitro. *Cell Res* 30, 269-271, 2020.
2. Huang, M., Tang, T., Pang, P., Li, M., Ma, R., Lu, J., Shu, J., You, Y., Chen, B., Liang, J., Hong, Z., Chen, H., Kong, L., Qin, D., Pei, D., Xia, J., Jiang S., Shan H., Treating COVID-19 with Chloroquine, *Journal of Molecular Cell Biology*, mjaa014, 2020.
3. Gautret P, Lagier JC, Parola P, Hoang VT, Meddeb L, Mailhe M, Doudier B, Courjon J, Giordanengo V, Vieira VE, Dupont HT, Honoré S, Colson P, Chabrière E, La Scola B, Rolain JM, Brouqui P, Raoult D (2020) Hydroxychloroquine and azithromycin as a treatment of COVID-19: results of an open-label non-randomized clinical trial. *Int J of Antimi Agents*. 2020.
4. Chou AC, Fitch CD, Heme polymerase: modulation by chloroquine treatment of a rodent malaria, *Life Sci*. 51(26):2073-8, 1992.
5. Slater AF. "Chloroquine: mechanism of drug action and resistance in *Plasmodium falciparum*". *Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 57, 2-3 203-235, 1993.
6. Vincent MJ., et al. "Chloroquine is a potent inhibitor of SARS coronavirus infection and spread". *Virology Journal* 2 69, 2005.
7. Xue J., et al. "Chloroquine Is a Zinc Ionophore". *PLOS One* 9.10 e109180, 2014.
8. CS Gautam, Roosy Aulakh and Priyanka Bhateja, Potential Armamentarium to Contain COVID-19 Pandemic in Developing Countries: Be Prepared and Act Timely, *ACTA SCIENTIFIC PAEDIATRICS (ISSN: 2581-883X) Volume 3 Issue 4*, 2020.
9. Savarino A., et al. "New insights into the antiviral effects of chloroquine". *Lancet Infectious Diseases* 6.2 67-69, 2006.
10. Takeda K., et al. "Toll-Like Receptors". *Annual Review of Immunology* 21, 335-376, 2003.
11. Huang C., et al. "Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China". *Lancet* 395,10223 497-506, 2020.
12. Prasad AS. Zinc is an Antioxidant and Anti-Inflammatory Agent: Its Role in Human Health, *Frontiers in Nutrition* 1, 14, 2014.

13. Awotiwon AA., et al. "Zinc supplementation for the treatment of measles in children". *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 6 CD011177, 2017.
14. Velthuis AJW., et al. Zn (2+) inhibits coronavirus and arterivirus RNA polymerase activity in vitro and zinc ionophores block the replication of these viruses in cell culture. *PLOS Pathogens* 6.11 e1001176, 2010.
15. Zhang L and Liu Y. "Potential interventions for novel coronavirus in China: A systematic review". *Journal of Medical Virology* 92, 5 479-490, 2020.
16. Jane Achan, Ambrose O Talisuna, Annette Erhart, Adoke Yeka, James K Tibenderana, Frederick N Baliraine, Philip J Rosenthal and Umberto D'Alessandro, Quinine, an old anti-malarial drug in a modern world: role in the treatment of malaria, *Malaria Journal*, 10:144,2011.
17. Dobson SMaM: The history of antimalarial drugs. In *Antimalarial Chemotherapy: Mechanisms of Action, Resistance, and New Directions in Drug Discovery*. Edited by: PJ R. Totowa, New Jersey: Humana Press; 15-25, 2001.
18. Salako LA, Sowunmi A: Disposition of quinine in plasma, red blood cells and saliva after oral and intravenous administration to healthy adult Africans. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol* 42(2):171-174, 1992.
19. Jamaludin A, Mohamed M, Navaratnam V, Mohamed N, Yeoh E, Wernsdorfer W: Single-dose comparative kinetics and bioavailability study of quinine hydrochloride, quinidine sulfate and quinidine bisulfate sustained-release in healthy male volunteers. *Acta Leiden* 57(1):39-46,1988.
20. White NJ, Chanthavanich P, Krishna S, Bunch C, Silamut K: Quinine disposition kinetics. *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 16(4):399-403,1983.
21. Karlsson KK, Hellgren U, Alvan G, Rombo L: Audiometry as a possible indicator of quinine plasma concentration during treatment of malaria. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg* 84(6):765-767,1990.
22. Alex Zhavoronkov, Vladimir Aladinskiy, Alexander Zhebrak, Bogdan Zagribelnyy, Victor Terentiev, Dmitry S. Bezrukov, Daniil Polykovskiy, Rim Shayakhmetov, Andrey Filimonov, Philipp Orekhov, Yilin Yan, Olga, Popova, Quentin Vanhaelen, Alex Aliper, Yan Ivanenkov, Potential COVID-2019 3C-like Protease Inhibitors Designed Using Generative Deep Learning Approaches, ChemRxiv.

23. Ji, W., Wang, W., Zhao, X., Zai, J. & Li, X. Homologous recombination within the spike glycoprotein of the newly identified coronavirus may boost cross-species transmission from snake to human. *J. Med. Virol.* 2020.
24. de Wilde, A. H., Snijder, E. J., Kikkert, M. & van Hemert, M. J. Host Factors in Coronavirus Replication. *Curr. Top. Microbiol. Immunol.* 419, 1–42, 2018.
25. Song, Z. et al. From SARS to MERS, Thrusting Coronaviruses into the Spotlight. *Viruses* 11, .2019.
26. Xintian Xu, Ping Chen, Jingfang Wang, Jiannan Feng, Hui Zhou, Xuan Li, Wu Zhong, Pei Hao, *Science China Life Sciences*, Volume 63, Issue 3: 457-460, 2020.
27. Renhong Yan, Yuanyuan Zhang, Yingying Guo, Lu Xia, and Qiang Zhou, Structural basis for the recognition of the 2019-nCoV by human ACE2, *bioRxiv*, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.19.956946>
28. Christine A. Hrycyna, Robert L. Summers, Adele M. Lehane, Marcos M. Pires, Hilda Namanja, Kelsey Bohn, Jerrin Kuriakose, Michael Ferdig, Philipp P. Henrich, David A. Fidock, Kiaran Kirk, Jean Chmielewski, and Rowena E. Martin, Quinine Dimers Are Potent Inhibitors of the *Plasmodium falciparum* Chloroquine Resistance Transporter and Are Active against Quinoline-Resistant *P. falciparum*, *ACS Chem Biol.* 9(3): 722–730, 2014.
29. A C MacIntyre, D J Cutler , The potential role of lysosomes in tissue distribution of weak bases, *Biopharmaceutics & Drug Disposition* 9(6):513-26, 2006.
30. Bauernfeind, F, Ablasser, A., Bartok, E., Kim, S., Schmid-Burgk, J., Cavlar, T., et al. Inflammasomes: current understanding and open questions. *Cell Mol. Life Sci.* 68, 765–783, (2011).
31. Tschopp, J., and Schroder, K. NLRP3 inflammasome activation: the convergence of multiple signalling pathways on ROS production? *Nat. Rev. Immunol.* 10, 210–215, (2010). doi: 10.1038/nri2725
32. I-Yin Chen, Miyu Moriyama, Ming-Fu Chang and Takeshi Ichinohe, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus Viroprotein 3a Activates the NLRP3 Inflammasome, *Front. Microbiol.*, 29 January 2019 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.00050>

33. Joy G. Mohanty, Erika Nagababu, and Joseph M. Rifkind, Red blood cell oxidative stress impairs oxygen delivery and induces red blood cell aging, *Front Physiol.* 5: 84, 2014.
34. Fibach and Rachmilewitz, The role of oxidative stress in hemolytic anemia, *Curr. Mol. Med.* 8(7):609-19, 2008.
35. Nagababu E., Rifkind J.M. Formation of fluorescent heme degradation products during the oxidation of hemoglobin by hydrogen peroxide. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 247:592–596, 1998.
36. Scott R. Zavada, Tsatsral Battsengel and Timothy F. Scott, Radical-Mediated Enzymatic Polymerizations, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 17, 195, 2016.
37. Kadokawa, J., Kokubo, A., Tagaya, H., Free-radical polymerization of vinyl monomers using hematin as a biomimetic catalyst in place of enzyme, *Macromolecular Bioscience* 2(6): 257 - 260, 2002.
38. Fee JA, Todaro TR, Luna E, Sanders D, Hunsicker-Wang LM, Patel KM, Bren KL, Gomez-Moran, E, Hill MG, Ai JY, Loehr TM, Oertling WA, Williams PA, Stout CD, McRee D, Pastuszyn A., *Biochemistry* 43:12162–12176, 2004.
39. Sarah E. J. Bowman and Kara L. Bren, The Chemistry and Biochemistry of Heme c: Functional Bases for Covalent Attachment, *Nat Prod Rep.* 25(6): 1118–1130. 2008.
40. Upadhyay R, Rana R, Sood A, Maurya SK., Formic Acid-Driven Rapid and Green Anti-Markovnikov Hydrothiolation of Styrenes, *ACS Omega.* 4;4(12):15101-15106, 2019.
41. Dondoni A, Marra A. Recent applications of thiol-ene coupling as a click process for glycoconjugation. *Chem Soc Rev.* 41:573–586, 2012.
42. Valkevich EM, Guenette RG, Sanchez NA, Chen Y-c, Ge Y, Streiter ER. Forging isopeptide bonds using thiol-ene chemistry: Site-specific coupling of ubiquitin molecules for studying the activity of isopeptidases. *J Am Chem Soc.* 134:6916–6919, 2012.
43. Li Y, Yang M, Huang Y, Song X, Liu L, Chen PR. Genetically encoded alkenyl-pyrrolysine analogues for thiol-ene reaction mediated site-specific protein labeling. *Chem Sci.* 3:2766–2770, 2012.
44. Kathleen C. A. Garber¹ and Erin E. Carlson, Thiol-ene Enabled Detection of Thiophosphorylated Kinase Substrates, *ACS Chem Biol.* 8(8): 1671–1676, 2013.

45. E.J. Snijder, E. Decroly, and J. Ziebuhr, The Nonstructural Proteins Directing Coronavirus RNA Synthesis and Processing, *Adv Virus Res.* 96: 59–126, 2016.
46. Krishna Narayanan, Sydney I. Ramirez, Kumari G. Lokugamage, and Shinji Makino, Coronavirus nonstructural protein 1: Common and distinct functions in the regulation of host and viral gene expression, *Virus Res.* 202: 89–100, 2015.
47. Ziebuhr J. The coronavirus replicase. *Curr. Top. Microbiol. Immunol.* 2005; 287:57–94; Mielech A.M., Chen Y., Mesecar A.D., Baker S.C. Nidovirus papain-like proteases: multifunctional enzymes with protease, deubiquitinating and delSGylating activities. *Virus Res.* 194:184–190, 2014.
48. Zhou, P. et al. Discovery of a novel coronavirus associated with the recent pneumonia outbreak in humans and its potential bat origin. *Microbiology* 104, 2020.
49. Naina Barretto, Dalia Jukneliene, Kiira Ratia, Zhongbin Chen, Andrew D. Mesecar and Susan C. Baker, The Papain-Like Protease of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus Has Deubiquitinating Activity, 2015.
50. Fan, K. et al. Biosynthesis, purification, and substrate specificity of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 3C-like proteinase. *J. Biol. Chem.* 279, 1637–1642, 2004.
51. Thiel, V. et al. Mechanisms and enzymes involved in SARS coronavirus genome expression. *J. Gen. Virol.* 84, 2305–2315, 2003.
52. Goetz, D. H. et al. Substrate specificity profiling and identification of a new class of inhibitor for the major protease of the SARS coronavirus. *Biochemistry* 46, 8744–8752, 2007.
53. Aaron Volk et al., Coronavirus Endoribonuclease and Deubiquitinating Interferon Antagonists Differentially Modulate the Host Response during Replication in Macrophages, *Journal of Virology* PMID: 32188729, 2020.
54. Wang L. et al., Structural and biochemical characterization of SARS-CoV Papain Like protease 2, in *Protein Science*, PMID: 32216114, 2020.
55. Yong Hu, Wei Li, Ting Gao, Yan Cui, Yanwen Jin, Ping Li, Qingjun Ma, Xuan Liu, Cheng Cao, The Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus Nucleocapsid Inhibits Type I Interferon Production by Interfering with TRIM25-Mediated RIG-I Ubiquitination, *J Virol.* Apr 15; 91(8): e02143-16, 2017.

56. Amerik AY, Hochstrasser M. Mechanism and function of deubiquitinating enzymes. *Biochim Biophys Acta* 1695,189–207, 2004.
57. Komander D. Mechanism, specificity and structure of the deubiquitinases, *Subcell Biochem* 54, 69–87, 2010.
58. Judith A Ronau, John F Beckmann, and Mark Hochstrasser, Substrate specificity of the ubiquitin and Ubl proteases, *Cell Res.*, 26 (4) 441–456, 2016.
59. Ratia, K., Pegan, S., Takayama, J., Sleeman, K., Coughlin, M., Baliji, S., Chaudhuri, R., Fu, W., Prabhakar, B.S., Johnson, M.E., Baker, S.C., Ghosh, A.K., Mesecar, A.D. A noncovalent class of papain-like protease/deubiquitinase inhibitors blocks SARS virus replication. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 105, 16119-16124, 2008.
60. Cheng-Wen Lin, Kuan-Hsun Lin, Tsung-Han Hsieh, Shi-Yi Shiu, Jeng-Yi Li, *FEMS Immunology & Medical Microbiology*, Volume 46, Issue 3, 375–380, 2006.
61. Yanchen Zhou, Punitha Vedantham, Kai Lu, Juliet Agudelo, Ricardo Carrion, Jr, Jerritt W. Nunneley, Dale Barnard, Stefan Pöhlmann, James H. McKerrow, Adam R. Renslo, and Graham Simmons, Protease inhibitors targeting coronavirus and filovirus entry, *Antiviral Res.* 116: 76–84, 2015.
62. Antalis TM, Bugge TH, Wu Q. Membrane-anchored serine proteases in health and disease. *Prog Mol Biol Transl Sci* 99: 1–50, 2011.
63. Awen Menou, JanWillem Duitman, Pauline Flajolet, Jean-Michel Sallenave, Arnaud André Mailleux, and Bruno Crestan, Human airway trypsin-like protease, a serine protease involved in respiratory diseases, *Am J Physiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol* 312: L657–L668, 2017.
64. Naoko Iwata-Yoshikawa, Tadashi Okamura, Yukiko Shimizu, Hideki Hasegawa, Makoto Takeda, Noriyo Nagata, TMPRSS2 Contributes to Virus Spread and Immunopathology in the Airways of Murine Models after Coronavirus Infection, *J Virol.* 93(6): e01815-18, 2019.
65. Tong Meng, Hao Cao, Hao Zhang, Zijian Kang, Da Xu, Haiyi Gong, Jing Wang, Zifu Li, Xingang Cui, Huji Xu, Haifeng Wei, Xiuwu Pan, Rongrong Zhu, Jianru Xiao, Wang Zhou, Liming Cheng, Jianmin Liu, The transmembrane serine protease inhibitors are potential antiviral drugs for 2019-nCoV targeting the insertion sequence-induced viral infectivity, 2020.

66. Shilpa Nimishakavi, Wilfred W. Raymond, Dieter C. Gruenert, and George H. Caughey, Divergent Inhibitor Susceptibility among Airway Lumen-Accessible Tryptic Proteases, *PLoS ONE* 10(10):e0141169, 2015.
67. Katz BA1, Clark JM, Finer-Moore JS, Jenkins TE, Johnson CR, Ross MJ, Luong C, Moore WR, Stroud RM, Design of potent selective zinc-mediated serine protease inhibitors, *Nature*. 391(6667):608-12, 1998.
68. Verner E, Katz BA, Spencer JR, Allen D, Hataye J, Hruzewicz W, Hui HC, Kolesnikov A, Li Y, Luong C, Martelli A, Radika K, Rai R, She M, Shrader W, Sprengeler PA, Trapp S, Wang J, Young WB, Mackman RL, Development of serine protease inhibitors displaying a multicentered short (<2.3 Å) hydrogen bond binding mode: inhibitors of urokinase-type plasminogen activator and factor Xa. *J Med Chem.*,44(17):2753-71, 2001.
69. Lee CC1, Kuo CJ, Hsu MF, Liang PH, Fang JM, Shie JJ, Wang AH., Structural basis of mercury- and zinc-conjugated complexes as SARS-CoV 3C-like protease inhibitors, *FEBS Letters* 581(28):5454-8, 2007.
70. Uchide N, Ohyama K, Bessho T, Yuan B, Yamakawa T, Effect of antioxidants on apoptosis induced by influenza virus infection: inhibition of viral gene replication and transcription with pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate. *Antiviral Res* 56: 207–217, 2002.
71. Suara RO, Crowe JEJ, Effect of zinc salts on respiratory syncytial virus replication. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 48: 783–790, 2004.
72. Aartjan J. W. te Velthuis, Sjoerd H. E. van den Worm, Amy C. Sims, Ralph S. Baric, Eric J. Snijder, Martijn J. van Hemert, Zn²⁺ Inhibits Coronavirus and Arterivirus RNA Polymerase Activity In Vitro and Zinc Ionophores Block the Replication of These Viruses in Cell Culture, *PLoS Pathogens*, Volume 6, Issue 11, e1001176, 2010.
73. Yan Gao, Liming Yan, Yucen Huang, Fengjiang Liu, Yao Zhao, Lin Cao, Tao Wang, Qianqian Sun, Zhenhua Ming, Lianqi Zhang, Ji Ge, Litao Zheng, Ying Zhang, Haofeng Wang, Yan Zhu, Chen Zhu, Tianyu Hu, Tian Hua, Bing Zhang, Xiuna Yang, Jun Li, Haitao Yang, Zhijie Liu, Wenqing Xu, Luke W. Guddat, Quan Wang, Zhiyong Lou, Zihao Rao, Structure of RNA-dependent RNA Polymerase from COVID-19 virus, *Science*, 10.1126, 2020.
74. Peng TY, Lee KR, Tarn WY.. Phosphorylation of the arginine/serine dipeptide-rich motif of the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus nucleocapsid protein modulates its

multimerization translation inhibitory activity and cellular localization, FEBS J, 275:4152-4163, 2008.

75. Wu CH, Yeh SH, Tsay YG, Shieh YH, Kao CL, Chen YS, Wang SH, Kuo TJ, Chen DS, Chen PJ.. Glycogen synthase kinase-3 regulates the phosphorylation of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus nucleocapsid protein and viral replication. J Biol Chem. 284:5229-5239, 2009.

76. Yingying Cong, Mustafa Ulasli, Hein Schepers, Mario Mauthe, Philip V'kovskic, Franziska Kriegenburg, Volker Thielc, Cornelis A.M. de Haan, Fulvio Reggioria, Nucleocapsid protein recruitment to replication-transcription complexes 2 plays a crucial role in coronaviral life cycle, J. Virol. doi:10.1128/JVI.01925-19. Online 27 November 2019.

77. Roland Hubel, Kurt Polborn , Wolfgang Beck. "Cinchona Alkaloids as Versatile Ambivalent Ligands – Coordination of Transition Metals to the Four Potential Donor Sites of Quinine", Eur. J. Inorg. Chem., 4712482, 1999.

78. Joshua Ayoola Obaleye, Mino R. Caira, Adedibu C. Tella, "Synthesis, Characterization and Crystal Structure of a Polymeric Zinc(II) Complex Containing the Antimalarial Quinine as Ligand", J Chem Crystallogr 37: 707–712, 2007.

79. Wenzhong L, Hualan L., COVID-19: Attacks the 1-Beta Chain of Hemoglobin and Captures the Porphyrin to Inhibit Human Heme Metabolism, ChemRxiv, 2020.

80. Roumenina L. T., Rayes, J., Lacroix-Desmazes S., and Dimitrov J. D., Heme: Modulator of Plasma Systems in Hemolytic Diseases, Trends in Molecular Medicine, 22, 3, 2016.

81. Sparkenbaugh, E. M., Chanrathammachart, P., Wang, S, Jonas, W, Kirchhofer, D., Gailani, D., Gruber, A., Kasthuri, R., Key, N. S., Mackman, N. and Pawlinski, R., Excess of heme induces tissue factor-dependent activation of coagulation in mice, haemadoi:10.3324/haematol.2014.114728 tologhaematologica

82. David J. Sullivan Jr., Quinolines block every step of malaria heme crystal growth, PNAS 114 (29) 7483-7485, 2017.

83. Alumasa JN, et al. The hydroxyl functionality and a rigid proximal N are required for forming a novel non-covalent quinine-heme complex. J Inorg Biochem 105:467–475, 2011.

84. Gorka AP, de Dios A, Roepe PD Quinoline drug-heme interactions and implications for antimalarial cytostatic versus cytocidal activities. *J Med Chem* 56:5231–5246, 2013.

85. de Villiers, K. A., Gildenhuis, J. and le Roex, T., Iron(III) Protoporphyrin IX Complexes of the Antimalarial Cinchona Alkaloids Quinine and Quinidine, *ACS Chem. Biol.* 7, 666–671, 2012.